

DEMOGRAPHIC CALENDAR

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DEMOGRAPHY IN PERSONS, EVENTS, DOCUMENTS. MEMORABLE DATES 2017.

Abstract. Dear Readers! The purpose of this section is to remind of what is important to population specialists, what deserves to be preserved in our memories. We are not the “Ivans with no memory of kinship.” We remember our kinship, respect our history — the history of the Science School of Dmitry Ignatievich Valentey, respect and preserve the traditions of our Center for Population Studies of the Faculty of Economics of Lomonosov MSU, the 50th anniversary of which is only a little away.

Anniversaries and round dates are a good occasion to recall the memorable dates of our teachers and colleagues, both living and those who had passed from this life, of their contribution to the development of population and demography economics, the neighbouring demographic sciences and the population knowledge system, to recall publications and conferences, laws and concepts, and all important to understand the ways in which modern knowledge of the country’s demographic development and the world was established.

And if you’re considering how to begin a lecture or a new article, start with the “lesson” of memory ...

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This year we celebrated **the 95th anniversary of Dmitry Ignatievich Valentey** (15.09.1922 – 17.12.1994) and **the 50th anniversary of the** department of population, which he established at the Faculty of Economics of MSU (September 1967). These anniversaries coincided with the **Ninth Valentievsky Readings, the**

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International Scientific Conference on “Demographics Education and population research at universities” (18–20 October 2017)¹.

The proceedings of the conference are published in a compendium issued at the beginning of the conference.² In addition, as a result of the readings held, some of the reports have been published in the “Statistics and Economics” journal, 2017, No. 5 2017.³

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We recall several important round dates from the history of demography and population policy, which 2017 was rich with.

355 years ago, in 1662, the work of the Englishman John Graunt (1620-1674), “**Natural and Political Observations Made upon the Bills of Mortality**”, was published, which initiated research into the reproduction of the population. That year can be regarded as the year of the Birth of demography as science. What J. Graunt wrote about three and a half centuries ago is relevant today: «... *The foundation and indispensable parts of a fair and harmless policy are to know the land and the workers that inhabit it. [...]... how many people live there of each sex, marital status, age, religion, type of occupation, rank or title, etc. Knowing that, it is possible to make industries and management of the state more reliable and correct*”⁴.

90 years ago, the **first World Population Conference was held**. It was held in late August — early September 1927 in Geneva. The Initiator - Margaret Sanger, the founder of the “American League for Birth Control” and, subsequently, the “International Family Planning Association”. Among the 123 delegates from 26 countries were renowned scholars such as Alexander Carr-Saunders, Corrado Gini, Robert Kuchinsky, Raymond Pearl and others. Various aspects of population growth and its relationship to resources, issues of optimum population, fertility, international migration and its limitations and other matters were discussed at the conference. The social, economic and political consequences of population growth were perceived as a threat that could change civilization and possibly eventually destroy it. The conference was aimed at finding a response to this challenge: “*To make the first preliminary step to an intellectual answer to this question and to the practical actions that this response should take*”⁵.

¹ See the programme of the Valentievsky readings, the conference compendium, the department's anniversary interview and other materials on the website of the department of population https://demography.econ.msu.ru/Valentey_seminar/

² <https://www.econ.msu.ru/sys/raw.php?o=43482&p=attachment>.

³ <http://statecon.rea.ru/jour/issue/current>

⁴ Introduction to Demography. M., 2002, pp. 5-6.

⁵ <http://demoscope.ru/weekly/2017/0737/nauka01.php>

Eighty years ago, in January 1937, the **All-union census** was held, later named the “firing squad” census. By a special decree of the Council of People’s Commissars, the census “was declared to have been carried out with the severe violation of the elementary fundamentals of statistical science as well as in violation of government-approved instructions, its organization was recognized unacceptable, the material - defective, the statisticians responsible for its conduct were repressed, and a new census was appointed in January 1939.”¹ The head of the Central Statistical Administration A. D. Kraval and the head of the Central Statistical Administration Census Bureau O. A. Kvitkin, who were responsible for the preparation and conduct of the census, were executed by firing squad and a number of census executives were repressed for the preparation and conduct of the census. The provisional figures on the population of the USSR were very far from those expected by the government - they were much less. The census materials were confiscated and classified, and the archived results were published only in 1990.

50 years ago, the **D. I. Valentey’s monograph “Population Theory and Policy”** (M.: Higher School, 1967) was issued. That’s what he wrote of half a century ago:

«... *The theory, — (for D. I. Valentey this is Marx-Lenin theory) — allows us to define our attitude towards specific-sociological, including specific-demographic research, the purpose of which is to define population policies, its implementation is of interest to society. ... Issues related to the birth rate are of particular importance. The birth rate in our country is steadily dropping. In a known part of the Soviet Union, even simple reproduction of the generation is not ensured. In this regard, certain legislative measures, some public policies that meet the needs of the time, are needed.... The issue of granting significant maternity benefits to mothers at the birth of a second and third child, rather than encouraging the birth of 9 and 10 children, should be raised in some of the Union republics... Despite the fact that abortion has become excessively widespread in our country, we do not at all consider the legal prohibition of abortion appropriate, as the inevitable consequence of such a ban is the widespread use of criminal abortions — it will in many cases have very serious consequences for women.*

How to change the parameters of reproduction of the population in those areas where they are disadvantaged? How to increase the birth rate there? It must be thought of today.”²

It’s been **45 years** since the **graduation of demographers of 1972**. It was the second graduation of economists who had been specialized in the Department

¹ Volkov A. G. Population census of 1937: fiction and truth //Census of the USSR population of 1937. History and materials / Express information. “Statistics History” Series. Issues 3-5 (part II). M., 1990/ C. 6-63 -http://demoscope.ru/weekly/knigi/polka/gold_fund08.html.

² *Valentey D. I. Population Theory and Policy*. M.: Higher School; 1967. pp. 6, 163-164.

of Population. Congratulations to my colleagues: Natalia Zvereva, Tamara Fedotovskaya, Sergei Smidovich, Yuri Avdeyev and others, who had tied their fate to demographics.

40 years ago, in September 1977, the MCC CPSU and the Executive Committee of Moscow Council adopted a decree **“On the status and measures to improve the demographic situation and to stimulate the natural growth of the population of the city of Moscow.”**¹ The paper was prepared with the active participation of D. I. Valenty (he was vice-chairman of the Moscow Commission on Labour Resources). It provided for the further improvement of maternal and child healthcare, the improvement of working conditions for working women, housing conditions, provision of childcare facilities, etc. In order to implement the goals and objectives of the population policy in this document, a regional program to improve the demographic situation was adopted in Moscow, the first in the RSFSR. A year later, such a program was adopted by the Bashkir ASSR (1978).

35 years ago in Saratov (1982), and **30 years** ago in Yoshkar-Ola (1987) All-union conferences (seminar schools) on population development management issues were held. The initiators of the seminar schools, which are important for the science and practice of population forums, and the unchanged chairman of the Organization Committee was D. I. Valenty.

35 years ago, a monograph of our Ukrainian colleagues, **“Population policy: Implementation and improvement in the context of developed Socialism”** (editor V. S. Steshenko, Kiev: Naukova Dumka, 1982), was published. The authors wrote that “the population policy of a developed socialist society is aimed at achieving a demographic objective, the essence of which is to *transform the socialist population into a communist population*, in other words it aims at the formation of a communist type of population reproduction - such a system of social relations that shapes and organizes the process of producing comprehensive, harmoniously developed people.”² The authors argued with the proponents of the development of the benefit system: «...You cannot recognize the recommendations of demographers offering to begin material stimulation of fertility by paying substantial benefits to the family budget for the second and third child economically reasonable and justified (at least in the current context)”. The alternative to child benefits was seen in the development of public consumption funds, in

¹ <http://mos80.ru/moscow/population.html>

² Demographic policy: implementation and improvement in the context of developed socialism. Kiev: Naukova Dumka, 1982. P. 49.

free forms of servicing families “consisting of the number of children needed by society”. These included families with “two or more children”.¹

35 years ago, most of the USSR began to implement the measures provided for in the Decree of the Central Committee of the Communist Party and the Council of Ministers of the USSR of 22 January 1981 No. 235 “**On measures to strengthen State assistance to families with children**”. The document contained fundamentally new principles and measures to support the family. The official interpretation of the objectives of the measures adopted was to create better conditions for population growth and to bring up the rising generations. The measures were introduced in stages, by region of the country: from 1 November 1981 — in the regions of the Far East, Siberia, in the northern parts of the European part of the RSFSR, and since 1 November 1982 - in the rest of the regions of the RSFSR, in the Ukraine, in Belarus, Moldova and the Baltic republics. Since 1983 the measures were extended to the republics of Central Asia and the Transcaucasus.

30 years ago the Central Commission of the Communist Party, the Council of Ministers of the USSR and the All-Union Central Council of Trade Unions adopted Decree No. 825 of 17 July 1987 “**On strengthening the implementation efforts of active social policies and enhancing the role of the State Committee on Labor of the USSR**”, which placed the responsibility for the formulation of population policies on the State Committee on Labor. The decree stated: “In view of the critical importance of population issues, to activate the work on implementation of effective population policies, raising it to the national level.” To ensure wide development and progressive implementation of socio-economic measures for population development, the advancement of the position of women, youth, the elderly, family formation, and the preservation and promotion of public health. Particular attention should be paid to the implementation of population measures in areas with a complex demographic situation, as well as to the high employment of women and the scarcity of labour resources. The planned targets for the development of the nation’s economy, the improvement of its structure and the deployment of productive forces are intrinsically linked to the solution of population issues. Consider it appropriate to develop within the Integrated program for social development and advancement of public welfare the forecasts of growth and restructuring of the country’s population, the improvement of the utilization of labour resources, the achievement of full employment of the population and also to organize the

¹ Demographic policy: implementation and improvement in the context of developed socialism. Kiev: Naukova dumka, 1982. P. 344.

preparation of regional population programs, taking into account the demographic characteristics of the regions”.¹

20 years ago, in 1997, the first two issues of the **informational bibliographic newsletter, “Demography and socio-economic issues of population”**, were released.² The structure of the publication was formed: an official section, a thematic selection of information materials and, finally, an index of population literature issued over a certain period of time. Whereas in issue No. 1 the index had 14 sections, in issue 2 there were already 24. In subsequent editions, which were published fairly regularly, the structure of the materials was clarified and the categories in index of literature was complemented.

15 years ago, in October 2002, the All-Russian census of the population took place, the first in the history of modern Russia. Initially it was planned for 1999. The census was held from the 9th to the 10th of October as of 0:00 9th October 2002. The results of the census were published in 14 volumes and are available on Rosstat’s website³.

10 years ago, by the Presidential Decree of 9 October 2007 No. 1351 the **“Concept of population policy of the Russian Federation for the period to 2025”**⁴ was adopted, which set out the goals, principles, objectives and major population policy directions for the period up to the year 2025. Population policies were declared to have the goal of stabilizing the population at 142–143 million people by 2015 and the creation of conditions for its growth to 145 million by 2025, as well as improving the quality of life and life expectancy by 2015 to 70 years, by 2025 — to 75 years. It was scheduled to increase the total fertility rate by 1.5 times by 2025 compared to 2006, and to reduce the death rate by 1.6 times. Implementation of the Concept is carried out in three stages. **In the first phase (2007–2010)**, measures were implemented to overcome the current negative trends in demographic development, and regional population programs had been developed in the constituent entities of the Russian Federation. As a result of implementing the measures of the first phase, natural attrition rates have been significantly reduced and significant migration growth has been achieved. As a result of imple-

¹ http://www.libussr.ru/doc_ussr/usr_14153.htm

² Literature on population. Information and bibliography index of literature issued in 1995. Issue No. 1. - Edited by V. V. Elizarov and A. A. Avdeev. M.: Dialogue - Lomonosov Moscow State University, 1997, p. 67; Literature on population. Information and bibliography index of literature issued in 1996. Issue No.2. - Edited by V. V. Elizarov and I. V. Dzerasova. M.: Dialogue-Lomonosov Moscow State University, 1997, p.48.

³ <http://www.perepis2002.ru/index.html?id=9>

⁴ <http://base.garant.ru/191961/>

menting the **second phase (2011–2015)**, the following was scheduled by 2016: stabilize the population at 142–143 million people; increase life expectancy to 70 years; increase the total fertility rate by 1.3 times by the year 2006, to reduce the mortality rate by one third; to reduce the outflow of skilled personnel, to increase the involvement of compatriots living abroad, qualified foreign professionals and young people in the Russian Federation for permanent residence and to ensure, on that basis, migration growth at a level of at least 200 thousand people annually. The birth rate had indeed increased by 1.3 times, life expectancy had exceeded 71 years, the migration rate had surpassed the target, however mortality had fallen by only 12%. **In the third phase (2016–2025)**, a preventative response should be undertaken to the possible deterioration of the demographic situation in the country. The concept envisages that, in view of the significant decline in the number of women of reproductive age at the beginning of the third phase, additional measures will be required to encourage the birth of the second and third child in families. In order to replace the natural decline of the population as a result of the possible reduction in the birth rate, it was planned to intensify work to attract immigrants of working age to permanent residence in the Russian Federation and to ensure migration growth of over 300 thousand people annually. A Plan of action for 2016–2020 is currently being implemented, which targets an increase in the population to 147.5 million by the year 2020, in life expectancy to 74 years; in the total fertility rate to the level of 1.87; ensuring that the rate of migration is at least 200 thousand people annually.¹

Five years ago, in the newspaper “Komsomolskaya Pravda” of February 13, 2012, V. V. Putin’s article (in essence, the candidate for Presidency pre-election program) “**Building Justice**” was published. **Social policy for Russia**”. The article also dealt with demographic issues: “*Today 143 million people live in Russia. Experts estimate that under the inertial scenario — that is, under the preservation of existing and absence of new measures — by 2050 it will be about 107 million people. If we manage to formulate and implement an effective, integrated population strategy, the Russian population will increase to 154 million people. Thus, the historic price of choosing between action and inaction is almost 50 million human lives in the next 40 years... The State shall take measures to support the aspirations of families to the birth of a second and subsequent children. These measures, particularly the introduction of maternal capital, have begun to yield first results. The birth rate is increasing, and it’s very gratifying... It is absolutely intolerable for a child to bring a family to the brink of poverty. Completely excluding such a situation is a national task for the next 3-4 years. ... I propose introducing in the constituent entities of the Federation, where negative demographic trends persist, special allowances for fami-*

¹ <http://government.ru/docs/22743/>

*lies at the birth of the third and subsequent children, until they reach the age of three, in the amount of the child's subsistence level... The family will be able to apply for a child benefit if it has an income per person, for example, not higher than the regional average... A "smart" migration policy based on clear requirements and criteria, excluding potential ethnocultural and other risks, will be objectively required to solve population problems. There will have to be a migration influx of about 300 thousand people per year."*¹

5 years ago, presidential decrees of 07.05.2012 No. 606 "**On measures for the implementation of the population policy of the Russian Federation**" and "**On the improvement of state health policy**" No. 598 were adopted, which set target indicators by 2018: increasing the total fertility rate (up to 1.753), improving life expectancy (up to 74 years)² and reducing mortality from individual causes.³

5 years ago, the Russian government issued the Decree of 31.05.2012, No. 535, "**Issues of the Ministry of Labour and Social security of Russia**".

The enumeration of areas of responsibility began with demography (!): «... The Ministry of Labour and Social Security of the RF is the federal executive body responsible for the formulation and implementation of state policies and regulations in the fields of *demography*, labour, standard of living and income, wages, pensions, ... labour migration, ... social security and social services for the population, including the social protection of the family, women and children".

5 years ago the National action strategy for the interests of children for 2012-2017 was adopted (Decree of the President of the Russian Federation of 1.06.2012 No. 761)⁴. The high risk of poverty at the birth of children, especially in large and single-parent families, was identified as one of the major problems of childhood. Family policy for childhood preservation was identified as the main focus of the Strategy. Priority measures included the drafting and adoption of a federal law defining the foundations of state family policy, as well as the development and adoption of minimum state guarantees in the fields of income and social services, defining the basic indicators of the quality of life of families with children, improving the system of tax deductions for families with children. The national strategy for the interests of children also included sections on the development of child-friendly healthcare, the new principle of the participation of children in all decisions affecting their interests and other sections. In continuation of the completed Strategy, the Decade of childhood was declared in the country (De-

¹ <https://www.kp.ru/daily/3759/2807793/>

² <http://base.garant.ru/70170932/>.

³ <http://base.garant.ru/70170948/>.

⁴ <http://base.garant.ru/70183566/>.

cree of the President of the Russian Federation of 29.05.2017 No. 240 “On the proclamation of the Decade of Childhood in the Russian Federation”).

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2017 is an anniversary year for our distinguished colleagues, whose names are known to the entire Russian demographic community and to many foreign colleagues.

In February 2017 *Valentina Vasilievna Bodrova* turned **80 years** old, who, after years of work at the Center for population issues research became one of the leading specialists in the Russian Public Opinion Research Center (VTsIOM).

In March *Valentina Mikhailovna Moiseenko*, a professor, renowned migration and historical demographer, chief research associate, and a former head of the sector of the population of Moscow and later head of the migration branch of our Center celebrated her **80-year** anniversary.

In September 2017 *Raisa Sergeevna Rotova*, known for her work in the field of population economics, and longstanding senior secretary of the “Population” compendium turned **85**.

In November 2017 *Tatiana Konstantinovna Smolina* celebrated her **80th birthday** — she was the first to be employed by the population laboratory in 1965.

We wish our colleagues health and creative longevity.

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We also remember our teachers and senior colleagues who are no longer with us.

The year 2017 was the **90th anniversary** of professor *Dmitry Kuzmich Shelestov* (01.05.1927-11.12.2000), a historian and demographer,

the **85th anniversary** of professor *Boris Sergeevich Khorev* (12.06.1932-03.06.2003), the greatest specialist in economic geography, resettlement and regional demography, former head of our Center;

The 80th anniversary of *Rudolf Vartanovich Tatevosov* (07.02.1937-08.05.2007), a geographer, demographer, popular environment specialist, former director of our Center’s sector;

The 80th anniversary of *Victor Alexeevich Sysenko* (28.03.1937-08.06.2008), a sociologist, demographer, renowned professional in the field of family and marriage, former director of our Center’s sector.

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Let us also recall the anniversaries of scientists who had left an imprint on the study of population, on the memorable dates of our colleagues from other organizations, universities and institutions of Russia and the former Soviet Union.

In 2017 it was:

175 years from the birth of Alexander Ivanovich Chuprov (18.02.1842-08.03.1908), the Russian economics scientist, statistician, public official, associate member of the Petersburg academy of sciences, distinguished professor of the Imperial Moscow university, one of the organizers of the census of the population of Moscow of 1882;

145 years from the birth of *Sergey Alexandrovich Novoselsky* (17.08.1872-12.11.1953), one of the founders of the national health and demographic statistics, academician of the AMS USSR. Together with V. V. Paevsky participated in the creation of the USSR Demographic Institute of AS USSR in Leningrad (1930-1934).

140 years from the birth of *Sergei Arkadyevich Tomilin* (19.10.1877-19.07.1952), a prominent Soviet Ukrainian scientist, specialist in social hygiene, medical statistics and history of medicine, demography.

125 years from the birth of *Avdey Ilyich Gozulov* (17.04.1892-9.06.1981), a famous Russian demographer and sociologist, author of the fundamental work “The censuses of the USSR and capitalist countries (1936).

85 years from the birth of *Arnold Leonidovich Perkovsky* (16.01.1932-27.09.2005), a renowned scientist demographer, a major historical demographer, representative of the Ukrainian school of demography.

85 years since the birth of Natalia Mikhailovna Rimashevskaya (29.03.1932 – 04.04.2017), corresponding associate of RAS, founder and first director of the Institute for Socio-economic issues of the population of RAS, chief editor of the “Narodonaselenie” journal;

85 years since the birth of Victor Fedorovich Shukailo (11.06.1932-16.11.1983), a renowned Ukrainian mathematician and demographer, professor, doctor of engineering sciences.

Eighty years from the birth of Oleg Sergeevich Pchelintsev (25.07.1936-8.04.2006), doctor of economics, professor, head of the laboratory of regional problems of socio-economic development of IEF RAS.

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Vladimir Mikhailovich Shkolnikov’s **60th** birthday on 6 May, a renowned European Demographer, who, since 2000, is head the Laboratory of Demographic data at the Institute of Demographic Studies of the Max Plank society (Rostock, Germany), and also the scientific head of the Population Research Center of RES (2011-2016), and since 2017 the scientific leader of the international Research and Public Health laboratory of NRU HSE.

On 31 August *Pavel Markovich Polyán*, a Russian geographer, demographer, historian, literary and writer, leading scientific associate at the Institute of Geography of RAS celebrated his **65th anniversary**.

On September 10, *Sergey Alexeevich Vasin*, a senior associate of the Demography Institution of NRU HSE, turned **60**.

On 8 August, *Tatiana Mikhailovna Maleva*, director of the Institute for Social Analysis and forecasting RANEPА, a renowned social policy specialist, graduate of the Faculty of Economics of Lomonosov Moscow State University, celebrated her anniversary.

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In 2017, the following people left this life:

Natalia Mikhailovna Rimashevskaya (29.03.1992-404.04.2017), corresponding member of RAS, the founder and first director of the Institute for Socio-economic issues of the population of RAS, chief editor of the “Narodonaselenie” journal;

Ludmila Vyacheslavovna Makarova, the first associate who came to the Demography division of the Institute of Sociology of the AS USSR in January 1974. It worked in it and then, since 1992, at the Center for Social demography and economic sociology ISPR RAS for 43 years;

Giorgy Evgenyevich Tsuladze, a prominent Georgian demographer, doctor of historical sciences, professor, founder of the Institute of Demography and Sociology in the system of the Georgian Academy of Sciences;

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On the 4th of June, aged 68 years, the CEO of the United Nations Population Fund (UNFPA) *Babatunde Osotimehin* passed away suddenly. He led the Fund since 2011, at the same time performing the duties of the Secretary General of the United Nations Organization.